

Study Habits and Academic Achievement among Male & Female Secondary School Students

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Abstract

The Study was aimed to find out study habits of male and female students of secondary schools & To academic achievement of male and female of secondary schools students in Ruderpur district of Uttarakhand. Descriptive survey method was applied to collect data by administering Study Habit Inventory by Palsane and Sharma & 9th Class Board Examination scores of secondary school students was taken as academic achievement. A representative sample of total 100 students of tenth class from government and private schools was selected with the help of simple random sampling technique. Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' test were applied to analyse the data. The mean scores of male (57.30) and female (56.24) primary students indicates the male students have better study habits than female students. The mean scores of male (79) and female (81.20) primary students reveals that female students show better academic achievement than male students.

Keywords: Study Habits, Academic Achievement, Sec. School Students

Introduction

The study habit is one of the greatest students or learning factors that hugely influences students' academic achievements. If undermined by students at all levels, teachers, administrators, parents and guardians, school counselors and the government, then, the trend and menace of students' abysmal performance in both internal and external examinations would continue to boom and become more devastating and alarming.

Mark and Howard (2009) are of the opinion that the most common challenge to the success of students in all ramifications is a lack of effective or positive (good) study habit. They further maintain that if students can develop a good study habit and with good discipline, they are bound to perform remarkably well in their academic pursuit. Husain (2000) stresses that lack of effective or positive (good) study habits is a critical study problem among students at all levels. Grace (2013) also maintains that the process of learning is still a little mysterious but studies do show that the most effective process for studying involves highly active behavior over a period of time. In other words, to study effectively, one must read, draw, compare, memorize and test himself over time.

Attitude towards study has great contribution on academic achievement, and good study pattern. Successful learners adopt positive attitude towards study, and do not waste time or energy over what they have to do. If the learning experience is pleasant, the learner's attitude and motivation is usually positive, and if the learning experience is not pleasant he tends to avoid it. Negative attitude towards study sometimes finds expression in comment such as "I study but cannot remember what I study" or "the lessons are too long". Attitude serves as index on how we think and feel about people, objects and issues in our environment. Study attitude, according to Husain (2000), refers to the predispositions which students have developed towards private readings through a period of time. According to him, study attitude offers great possibilities for successful achievement in studies. Study method is the

knowledge and application of effective study skills or techniques by students. Several study methods have been identified several effective study methods and skills that could be used by students based on the learning environment (Husain, 2000). Kelli (2009) posits that for students to succeed in their studies, they must be able to appropriately assimilate course content, digest it, reflect on it and be able to articulate the information in written and/or oral form. What is fundamental is the ability of a student to acquire effective study habits. Many students feel that the hours of study are the most important. However, students can study for hours on end and retain very little. The more appropriate question is how students should study more effectively. Developing good time management skills is very important. Students must realize that there is a time to be in class, a time for study, time for family, time to socialize and time to just be alone. The critical issue is recognition that there must be an appropriate balance. Students should also have vision. A clearly articulated picture of the future they intend to create for themselves is very important and contributes to students' success in school. This will promote a passion for what they wish to do. Passion is critical and leads to an intense interest, dedication and commitment to achieving career goals and objectives.

Different students have different and unique study habits. What may be a good study habit to a particular student may be a bad one indeed to another student. As such, it is often difficult to practically pin-point that this is good and that is bad. In the opinion of Katelyn (2013), there is no doubt that different people study in different ways and it is a near certainty that what works for one person may not work for another. John (2010) opines that not all students are alike.

There are several key study habits that are crucial to all students' success. One of such is study in a good environment, a little bit of background music, such as classical with no lyrics are fine and a good studying location. Whether studying in rain or shine, day or night, what is most important is to be consistent and stay on one schedule.

Generally, study habits can be classified into two-good study habits, and bad study habits. Good study habits according to Katelyn (2013) are sometimes referred to as positive or productive study habits. As the name implies, they are those pleasant study habits which have the tendency to improve the academic performance of students or that seem to produce good results. They are the study habits which make students successful in their studies after developing and applying them throughout their academic career. Good study habits occur as a result of practice and knowing what methods are most effective for you as a student. When studying, stay away from distractions, such as the computer. Instead of procrastinating, work on a long term assignment daily, instead of studying the night before, study a little each night. Review what you learned in class every day when you get home, before Ebele and Olofu 585 starting homework. Also, a good tip is to review what you did in class the previous day at the beginning of class when you have a few minutes before the teacher starts talking. By learning the ways that you learn the best, you will be successful in your studies.

Statement of the Problem

The specific research proposed by the investigator will be to determine: "STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS "

Operational Definitions of the Terms

Academic Achievement: Academic achievement here means total marks obtained by student in 10th class examination will be considered as score Academic Achievement for present investigation.

Study Habits: Study habits are generic rather than specific in terms of its importance. It has very long reaching effect deep into the life of individuals and by cumulative and interactive effects in the society, study habits have been considered to be constituted of nine different kind of study behaviour. These are; comprehension, concentration, task orientation, study sets, interaction, drilling, supports, recording and language. Good study habits include, class participation, study time, use of textbook and recitation.

Significance of the Study

Learning can be immensely gratifying, but studying usually involves hard work. The first step towards effective study habits is to face up to this reality. One need not feel guilty if one doesn't look forward to studying. Once an individual accepts the premise that studying doesn't come naturally, it should be apparent that one needs to set up an organized programme to promote adequate study. Learning how to study is really a long-term process. As one goes on studying, one finds more techniques and methods that offer new information leading one on an interesting and successful direction. So, learning how to study or to develop good study habits is a lifelong process, and one should be ready to modify one's method of study according to the need of the time. The development of good study habits is the highway to the goals of an individual, whatever they are. A simple, small change in study habits makes a big difference in goal setting and organization of one's life. The success of an individual depends upon his study habits. Education is the manifestation of perfection already existing in man. The tool enabling this manifestation is study habits.

In order to improve the quality of education we must develop certain innovative strategies, which will enhance the educational standards. In addition to that from the student's side there must be some important steps, which form the basis for their academic achievement. Students' needs, requirements, abilities, capabilities, their pattern of studying etc. have been neglected for a long time and they were forced to learn the same thing, by the same method, by the same person in the same environment. Not only is it important that teachers recognize these diversities in their students, but also it is desirable that they value their study habits. Otherwise, even if appropriate strategies are developed and made available to teachers, there may be little proof of gain in the students. Our educational institutions should take into account basic human differences in their studying, thinking etc., to seek better means of individualized instruction for more effective studying (Arul Lawrence, 2013). Here the investigator thought that student's academic achievement and their excellence in studies depends mainly on their study habits, which is very much influential in their learning process. Hence, the investigator will try to explore the relationship of study habits and academic achievement of students.

Objectives

The following objectives are formulated for the proposed study:

1. To study the study habits of male and female students of secondary schools.
2. To study the academic achievement of male and female students of secondary schools.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated to empirically validate the above objectives:

- ❖ There is a significant difference between the study habits of male and female students of secondary schools
- ❖ There is a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female students of secondary schools.

Variables

The variables of the study:

- Study habits as the independent variable and;
- Academic achievement as the dependent variable.

Research Methodology

Research Method: Descriptive survey method was applied in the present study. Data was collected by administering already tested instrument to test the Study habits of secondary school students.

Population: All school students of tenth class from government and private schools in Rudrapur was considered the population for the study

Sampling Procedure: A representative sample of total 100 students of tenth class from government and private schools in Rudrapur was selected with the help of simple random sampling technique.

Tool Used for Data Collection

The following tool were employed for the purpose of collecting data from the selected subjects:

1. Study Habit Inventory by Palsane and Sharma.
2. 9th Class Board Examination scores of secondary school students will be taken as academic achievement.

Statistical Techniques To Be Used: Various statistical tool and techniques was used according to the requirement of the study. Mean, Standard Deviation, ‘t’ test.

Delimitations of the Study: The study was delimited to students of 10th class of government and private schools in Rudrapur district of Uttarakhand only. The study was further delimited to the 100 school students of tenth class from government and private schools in Rudrapur district.

DATA ANALISIS & INTERPRETATIONS

Difference between male and female students of secondary school in their the study habits

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Study Habit	Male	50	57.30	17.675	0.281	P>0.05 (0.779)Significant
	Female	50	56.24	19.939		

(At 5% level of significance, for df=98, the table value of ‘t’ is1.96)

Graph 1.1: Mean difference between the study habits of male and female students

While comparing the mean scores of male (57.30) and female (56.24) students, the male students have better study habits than female students. Thus, hypothesis, which stated, as “There exist a significant difference between the study habits of male and female students of secondary school” is accepted.

**Difference between male and female students of
Secondary School in their the Academic Achievement**

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Academic Achievement	Male	50	79	16.067	-0.703	P>0.05 (0.484)Significant
	Female	50	81.20	15.205		

(At 5% level of significance, for df=98, the table value of ‘t’ is1.96)

Graph 1.2: Mean difference between the academic achievement of male and female students

While comparing the mean scores of male (79) and female (81.20) students, the female students show better academic achievement than male students. Thus, hypothesis, which stated, as “There is a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female students of secondary school” is accepted

FINDINGS:

- The mean scores of male (57.30) and female (56.24) primary students, the male students have better study habits than female students.
- The mean scores of male (79) and female (81.20) primary students, the female students show better academic achievement than male students.

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